

**DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATION OF CALCULATION TOOL FOR
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF CALCIUM LOOPING PILOT PLANT**

Lappeenranta–Lahti University of Technology LUT

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ABSTRACT

Lappeenranta–Lahti University of Technology LUT

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Development and Application of Calculation Tool for Performance Evaluation of Calcium Looping Pilot Plant

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Global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reached an all-time high of 57.1 GtCO₂e in the year 2023. The Paris Agreement takes action to limit the GHG emissions and global warming by a set of goals, laws and legislations. These incentivise development and deployment of technologies such as carbon capture, which is a crucial technology as nearly 70 % of GHG emissions consist purely of CO₂. Calcium looping (CaL) is a promising carbon capture technology that utilizes the reversible carbonation reaction of lime in a cyclic system to capture CO₂ from flue gases.

The objective of the thesis was to develop a calculation tool in MS Excel with macros written in Visual Basic for Applications and apply it to the experimental data from the La Pereda CaL pilot plant. The tool was used to solve the material and heat balances and obtain derived process parameters, as well as CaL specific key performance indicators for all relevant time intervals. The tool is related to scaling up of the CaL process and was therefore structured to facilitate future changes.

The development and application of the tool were successful, as the results were logical and in-line with those shown in previous studies. The main shortcomings in the tool arose from the accuracy of reactions and species-specific material imbalances both of which can be explained by the accuracy of measurements. The experiment examined in the thesis indicates that the plant was performing well, the material and heat balances for the entire unit were solved, and the derived KPIs are in line and greatly enhance the current state-of-the-art.

TIIVISTELMÄ

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Energiatekniikka, Energianmuuntoprosessit

Veikka-Joonatan Kalasniemi

Laskentatyökalun kehittäminen ja sen soveltaminen kalkkikiertoprosessin koelaitoksen suorituskyvyn arviointiin

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Avainsanat: hiilidioksidin talteenotto, hiilidioksidi, kalkkikiertoprosessi, päästöjen vähentäminen

Kasvihuonekaasupäästöt kasvoivat kaikkien aikojen ennätykseen vuonna 2023 saavuttaessaan 57,1 GtCO₂e. Pariisin ilmastopimuksen tavoitteena on rajoittaa näitä päästöjä sekä niiden aiheuttamaa ilmaston lämpenemistä lakien ja säädösten avulla. Nämä kannustavat teknologioiden, kuten hiilidioksidin talteenoton kehitystä ja käyttöönottoa. Hiilidioksidin talteenotto on erittäin tärkeä teknologia, sillä lähes 70 % kaikista päästöistä koostuu yksinomaan hiilidioksidista. Kalkkikiertoprosessi on lupaava hiilidioksidin talteenottomenelmä, joka hyödyntää kalkan reversiibeliä karbonoitumisreaktiota syklisessä prosessissa hiilidioksidin poistamiseen savukaasuista.

Työn tavoite oli kehittää laskentatyökalu MS Exceliä sekä Visual Basic for Applications makroja käyttäen ja soveltaa työkalua kalkkikiertoprosessin pilottilaitoksen kokeelliseen dataan. Luotu työkalu ratkaisee laitoksen energia- ja massataseen sekä laskee johdettuja prosessiparametrejä ja suorituskyvyn indikaattoreita valituille aikajaksoille. Työkalu liittyy teknologian mittakaavan kasvattamiseen teolliseen kokoluokkaan ja luotiin siksi helposti muokattavaksi.

Työkalun kehitys ja soveltaminen olivat onnistuneita, sillä tulokset olivat loogisia ja noudattivat aikaisempia tutkimuksia. Suurimmat puutteet työkalussa liittyivät reaktioiden tarkkuuteen ja ainekohtaisiin massataseisiin, joihin molempiin vaikuttivat mittausdatan tarkkuus. Työssä tarkasteltu laitoksen koeajo osoittaa, että laitos toimii koeajon aikana odotetusti. Saadut tulokset auttavat merkittävästi teknologian jatkokehittämisessä.

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Espoo, October 2025

Veikka-Joonatan Kalasniemi

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SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Roman characters

A	area	m^2
c	molar concentration	%
E	efficiency	%
F	molar flow rate	mol/s
G_s	specific solids transfer rate	$\text{kg}/(\text{m}^2\text{s})$
h	specific enthalpy	kJ/kg
i	gas species	-
k	deactivation constant	-
m	mass	kg
n	amount	mol
p	pressure	Pa
Q	heat	kW
r	mass ratio	-
T	temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}, \text{K}$
u	flow velocity	m/s
V	volume	m^3
W	inventory	kg
W_s	specific inventory	kg/m^2
X	carrying capacity	-
X_r	residual conversion capacity	-
X_{calc}	carbonate content at calciner outlet	%
X_{carb}	carbonate content at calciner inlet	%

Greek characters

λ	excess air factor	-
A	make-up ratio	$\text{mol}_{\text{CaCO}_3}/\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}$
Φ	solids transfer ratio	$\text{mol}_{\text{CaO}}/\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}$

Constants

g	gravity	9.81 m/s^2
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Subscripts

0	fresh
1	inlet
2	outlet
∞	prevailing
ave	average
eq	equilibrium
g	gas
ref	reference
s	solid
tot	total
R	cycled
CB	carbonator
CC	calciner
LS	loop seal

Abbreviations

CaL	Calcium Looping
CC	Carbon Capture
CFB	Circulating Fluidized Bed
DAC	Direct Air Capture
FA	Fly-Ash
FG	Flue Gas
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
PG	Product Gas
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HFC	Hydrofluorocarbon
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PFC	Perfluorocarbon
PPP	Purchasing Power Parity
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VBA	Visual Basic for Applications
WtE	Waste to Energy

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Symbols and abbreviations

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DECLARATIONS

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The originality of this thesis has been reviewed with the Turnitin similarity checking service.

AI usage & responsibility

The author of the thesis, Veikka-Joonatan Kalasniemi, used the following AI-tools during the preparation of the thesis:

1. ChatGPT 4o & 5
 - a. Purpose of use: Language proofing
 - b. Explanation of the use of the tool: To check the correctness of the words and the grammar used at certain sections of the work. Text was edited at some sections based on the suggestions received.

The author, Veikka-Joonatan Kalasniemi, takes full responsibility for the content of this thesis and has reviewed and edited the content generated by the use of AI tools.

1 Introduction

In 2023, total global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reached approximately 57.1 GtCO₂e (UNEP, 2024). The following year, total annual energy-related CO₂ emissions alone amounted to an all-time high of over 37.8 Gt of CO₂ (IEA, 2025). The record atmospheric CO₂ concentrations of 422.5 ppm were measured in 2024 representing an increase of over 50 % compared to pre-industrial levels. The GHG emissions from human activities have unequivocally caused the global surface temperature in 2011-2020 to rise 1.1 °C above the pre-industrial levels measured in 1850-1900 (IPCC, 2023). The on-going climate change has led to an observed increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather phenomena.

One of the most important actions taken to slow down and mitigate the effects of the climate change is the Paris Agreement, which was adopted by 196 parties at the United Nations Climate Conference (COP21) in 2015 (UNFCCC, 2015). The Paris Agreement is a legally binding international treaty on climate change. The aim of the treaty is to limit the increase of the global temperature below 2 °C above the pre-industrial levels by limiting GHG emissions and preferably further limit the warming to only 1.5 °C.

To reach the goal on the current pathway, in comparison to the year 2019, a reduction of 42 % in GHG emissions is required before 2030 and a reduction of 57 % by the end of 2035 (UNEP, 2024). The efforts towards the climate goals are driven and aided by legislations and laws such as the EU Fit for 55 package (European Council, 2025). The EU Fit for 55 is a package of laws that aims to reduce GHG emissions in the EU by at least 55 % by 2030. It is part of the European Green Deal strategy with an aim to reach net-zero GHG emissions by 2050 (European Commission, 2019).

Horizon Europe is a research and innovation funding programme adopted by the European Commission (2021), with one of its missions being to fund projects related to the European Green Deal and achieving the climate goals set by the different targets and laws. Decarbonization plays a crucial role in lowering the carbon emissions and slowing down the on-going climate change. One of the projects under the Horizon Europe is the project CaLby2030.

The main goal of CaLby2030 is to act as platform to achieve the commercial deployment of Calcium Looping (CaL) carbon capture (CC) technology to decarbonize industrial processes (CaLby2030, n.d.). The project focuses on high-energy and carbon-intensive industrial sectors such as iron & steel, cement, waste-to-energy (WtE), and bioenergy, where current technology does not allow for process-level CO₂ emission reductions.

The main objective of this thesis is the development of a calculation tool for evaluating the performance of the La Pereda CaL pilot plant during test campaigns. The tool is built in MS Excel and utilizes macros written in Visual Basic for Applications (VBA). The goals set for the calculation tool include that it calculates all relevant process variables across all time intervals and that it is structured in a way that it can be readily used or further developed to support potential future scale-up of the CaL process. The results focus on material and heat balance closure, and selected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as CO₂ capture rates, and material transfer rates. The KPIs are based on relevance for scale-up purposes as well as commonly used KPIs in previous literature for similar cases.

The first part of the thesis is a literature review that explores the current global carbon trends and describes the need for and technologies available for CC. The literature review also describes the CaL process in detail. The second part of the thesis is dedicated to describing the methods used in the calculation tool by dividing the section into data handling and process related parts. The third part presents results from the tool as figures and tables and discusses the meaning of them.

2 CO₂ Emission Mitigation via Carbon Capture

The impact of GHG emissions on the climate has received significant and increasing attention in the 21st century as the result of the human-caused climate change becoming more addressed. With global emissions continuing to rise despite international agreements and national policies, the need for effective mitigation strategies is greater than ever.

This chapter examines the current trends in the GHG emissions across the globe, investigates the current usage of CC and the potential for mitigations in CO₂ emissions utilizing CC. In addition, this chapter also reviews different CC technologies and their providers. Sequential steps in the CC value chain, such as storage, transportation and utilization of CO₂ are important parts that are required to achieve an efficient and successful CC industry. However, the descriptions of these steps are not included, as they are outside the scope of this work.

2.1 Emission Trends and Reduction Potential

The total GHG emissions in the year 2023 set a new record of 57.1 GtCO₂e, which is an increase of approximately 1.1 GtCO₂e or 1.3 % from the previous year when emissions of approximately 56 GtCO₂e were recorded. (UNEP, 2024). Figure 1 shows the total amount of GHG emissions in the year 2023 divided into sectors. By dividing the emissions into sectors, it becomes clear which sectors have the most effect on the emissions and therefore on the climate change. This is essential for designing effective mitigation strategies which are in line with the international climate targets such as the Paris Agreement.

Figure 1. Total GHG emissions in 2023 (UNEP, 2024)

The largest emitting sector is the power sector with approximately 26 % or 15 Gt of emissions. This highlights the need for decarbonization, especially through the transition to renewable energy sources. Second largest sector is the transport with 15 % or approximately 9 Gt of emissions. At third place is the industry sector with 11 % or approximately 6 Gt of emissions. These sectors have a wide range of opportunities for emission reduction each with their own challenges.

According to the classification in Kyoto Protocol (1997), the major GHGs responsible for causing the climate change include CO₂, methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O). Other powerful but less abundant GHGs include hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs) and sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆). Figure 2 shows how much each of the previously mentioned sectors emit each of the major GHGs. The share marked with F-gases includes the less abundant but powerful GHGs.

Figure 2. Share of main GHGs in global emissions by sector in 2023 (European Commission, 2024b)

As seen previously in Figure 1, the power industry, being the most emissive sector is also visible here in Figure 2. Along with transport, industrial combustion and buildings, the emissions of these sectors consist almost purely of CO₂ indicating that they have high potential for possible CC operations. On the other hand, for example the emissions of agriculture consist mostly of CH₄ and N₂O while the share of CO₂ is minimal. To support comparing the various emissions sources, a method of standardizing the emission intensity of the GHGs has been developed. This method compares how much each GHG contributes to the climate change in relation to CO₂. The multipliers for each GHG species are visible in Table 1.

Table 1. Global Warming Potential (GWP100) values relative to CO₂ for major GHGs (GHG Protocol, 2024)

Chemical	AR4	AR5	AR6
CO ₂	1	1	1
CH ₄ – non-fossil	25	28	27
CH ₄ – fossil	-	30	39.8
N ₂ O	298	265	273
NF ₃	17200	16100	17400
SF ₆	22800	23500	24300

The conversion of GHGs to CO_{2e} is standardized by the 100-year Global Warming Potential (GWP₁₀₀) defined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), with latest standard being the AR6 provided in the Sixth Assessment Report (IPCC, 2023). The GWP indicates the effective radiative forcing caused by the emission of a mass unit of a gas species accumulated over a time horizon relative to that of CO₂ (GHG Protocol, 2024). The calculation of the total GHG emissions in carbon dioxide equivalent (CO_{2e}) differs from source to source mainly due to the difficulty in estimating the emissions from forest fires as well as sources and sinks created by LULUCF (land-use, land-use change and forestry) (IPCC, 2023).

2.1.1 Emission Trends and Intensity

Despite the growing awareness and pressure by policies from different parties, the amount of GHG emissions still rise every year. The increase in GHG emissions happens mostly due to the current, practically unavoidable, increase in energy consumption and the ever-growing industry. The increase in electricity consumption can be observed clearly in Figure 3. In the figure it is presented with a grey colour and named “Main Activity Electricity and Heat Production” according to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories naming convention for emission sources (IPCC, 2006). This is among the fastest growing emissive sectors.

Figure 3. World CO₂ emissions trends 1971-2023 (European Commission, 2024b)

All the CO₂ emission sources in Figure 3 follow the IPCC 2006 naming scheme. Other notable changes visible in the chart are the increase in emissions related to road transport as well as the increase in manufacturing industries and construction. The impact of the global COVID-19 pandemic and the following economic recession is also clearly visible in the emission trends as is the effect of the 2008 financial crisis. On the more positive side in relation to CO₂ emission mitigation, the rapid increase between 2000 and 2010 has already shown signs of deceleration. Although total emissions have continued to rise, the amount emitted by different sectors in comparison to other sectors have remained relatively stable over the past decade. Before this period, and after with slightly less intensity, the most notable change in the proportions is the increase in electricity and heat production emissions.

Figure 4. Trends for top 10 CO₂ emitting countries (European Commission, 2024b)

As Figure 4 indicates, three of the most emitting countries are the following in decreasing order: China, United States and India. China has led the GHG emissions for approximately two decades surpassing the GHG emissions United States in 2004 after which it has reached an emission level that is multiple times higher than that of the following countries. However, during the past 12 months as of June 2025, the CO₂ emissions have decreased by 1 % while energy requirements have still been on the rising trend (CREA, 2025). This is the first time the growth in China's clean power generation has made an effect in the CO₂ emissions.

The United States was the top CO₂ emitting country until 2004, when China reached its levels, after which the emissions of the U.S. have actually been a downwards trend. According to EPA (2025), before 2007 the emissions increased at the same rate as the population, which resulted in the emissions remaining at a relatively constant level. The sharp decline between 2007 and 2009 is largely due to the 2008 U.S. economic crisis. The decrease after that is the result of the growing trend of replacing the carbon-intensive fossil fuels used in electricity and heat generation with natural gas and renewables.

The GHG emissions produced by India have been on a steady rise which has had slight acceleration since 2005 except during the COVID-19 pandemic. One of the main factors that plays in the constant increase of emissions is that India still actively utilizes heavily polluting fossil fuels such as coal and oil while less polluting options such as natural gas usage remains much the same.

Figure 5. World CO₂ emissions in comparison with CO₂ /capita and CO₂/GDP PPP (European Commission, 2024b; World Bank Group, 2024)

The red line, tCO₂/capita, in Figure 5 indicates the amount of CO₂ emissions per person per year. A slight rise can be observed after the year 2003 until the graph levels off at approximately 2010 with a slight downwards trend until 2023. Emissions per capita is an excellent indicator for the impact and the carbon footprint of an individual in a specific country.

The black line, tCO₂/\$M GDP, in Figure 5 indicates the amount of CO₂ emitted per GDP PPP (Gross Domestic Product, Purchasing Power Parity) per year. The GDP PPP adjusts the GDP to reflect the relative cost of goods and services indicating what people can afford to buy with the income they receive. The GDP PPP is shown with constant 2021 international dollar (Int\$) to remove the effects of inflation from the graph. Therefore, the CO₂/GDP PPP is a strong indicator for the actual achieved reduction in emissions as it directly compares emissions to how efficiently resources are converted into value.

The tCO₂/\$M GDP indicates a clear downwards trend that has been on-going since the start of the currently available data for GDP PPP. As stated by IEA (2025), the increase in global energy related CO₂ continues to decouple from the economic growth as the global economy expanded by more than 3 % in the year 2024 while the emission growth slowed down to 0.8 %.

2.1.2 Projected Pathways and Reduction Targets

Despite the downward trend in CO₂/GDP and the slight reductions in emission growth seen after 2010, according to the Emissions Gap Report by UNEP (2024), a continuation of the current mitigation efforts is estimated to result in limiting the global warming with a 66 % chance to a maximum of 3.1 °C over the course of the 21st century. The report also projects other scenarios on how certain amount of effort will affect the global warming and the likelihood of limiting the warming to a certain degree, the previously mentioned being the most pessimistic one. The most optimistic scenario has chance of 66 % in limiting the global warming to 1.9 °C when the UN countries have conditional Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).

Figure 6. Mitigation ranges for temperature limits (UNEP 2024)

UNEP (2024) also gives estimates for how much reduction is needed in order to stay on certain pathways. As mentioned in the beginning of the work, compared to 2019 levels, a reduction of 42 % in GHG emissions is required before the 2030 to get on a cost-effective pathway for 1.5 °C. Moreover, to stay on that pathway, a reduction of 57 % is required before 2035. Figure 6 presents these pathways along with some numbers regarding the amount of emissions. The orange marker “current aggregate NDC”, is the pathway with current policies and mitigation efforts.

2.1 Carbon Capture in CO₂ Emission Reduction

Carbon capture is a crucial technology that can help to achieve the emission targets and provide aid in limiting the rise of the global surface temperature. This subchapter focuses on defining the position of CC in emission reduction and lists methods and providers.

2.1.1 Carbon Capture Potential

CC has large potential to reduce emissions since CO₂ is the most abundant GHG emitted. Even though the GWP of, for example, CH₄ is significantly higher than that of CO₂, the reduction of CO₂ emissions is important as it still has the greatest global warming effect. The carbon-intensive industries that are potential targets for CC release CO₂ emissions that are hard or impossible to avoid using today's technologies. These industries include iron & steel, cement, WtE, and bioCHP.

The number of projects related to CC is growing faster than ever. According to the Global Status of CCS 2024 written by the Global CCS Institute (2024), during the last five years the installed CO₂ capture capacity has increased by approximately 20%, while the combined planned and operational CO₂ capture capacity has increased by more than three times.

The Global CCS Institute categorizes facilities under development into two categories. Facilities in "Early development" are ones that have either an on-going feasibility study or have already completed one. Facilities under the category "Advanced development" have completed thorough planning, for example via a front-end engineering and design.

Figure 7. Number of CC facilities and CO₂ capture capacity (Global CCS Institute, 2024)

In 2024, a total of 628 CC facilities were in the pipeline. This number includes operational plants as well as those under construction and in all stages of development. Since the year 2023 the number of operational CC facilities has increased by approximately 20 %, from 41 to 50 and those under construction have nearly doubled. The largest difference can be seen in the facilities that are under development with an increase of around 40 %.

The actual CO₂ capture capacity has increased by 4 % going from 2023 to 2024 while projects in early development have slightly lowered as they have moved into construction. The data indicates, that since the increase in the number of facilities is higher than actual capacity for all the categories, the facilities in question are smaller compared to existing ones.

According to data gathered by Global CCS Institute (2024), most of the currently operating CC facilities are related to either natural gas processing, hydrogen/ammonia/fertilizer production and power and heat generation. The new development is mostly set to be built during 2025 to 2030 for the previously mentioned sectors but additionally also focusing on cement, chemical production and direct air capture (DAC). Most of the current and new projects are located in Europe and North America with Asia-Pacific following behind.

Estimates vary from source to source, but for example IEA (2023) states in their net-zero emission scenario, that if all the currently announced projects are completed and the same

trend continues, in 2030 the capture capacity could reach up to 1 GtCO₂ and over 6 GtCO₂ in 2050.

2.1.2 Carbon Capture Methods and Technology Providers

CC refers to the process of capturing carbon in the form of CO₂. There are several methods for capturing CO₂, such as pre-combustion capture, capture during the process itself, post-combustion capture or for example capturing the CO₂ directly from the atmosphere. All of the mentioned methods refer to where or at which point of a process the CO₂ is captured. There are multiple techniques for executing the capturing of CO₂ for all the mentioned scenarios. CC, being a relatively new field, has a wide range of technologies under development at different stages with some of the most advanced being already in commercial operation. Technology readiness level (TRL) is a common standardized indicator which compares the readiness of technologies.

Table 2. CC technologies with TRL, providers and cost estimates (Hanson, et al. 2025; Global CCS Institute, 2025a; Global CCS Institute, 2025b; De Lena, et al. 2019)

Category	Usage	Providers / Utilizers	TRL	Costs USD/tCO ₂ **
Liquid Absorption*	post-combustion	SLB Capturi (Aker)	9	-
Solid Absorbent*	post-combustion, DAC	Svante	7	-
Membrane	post-combustion, oil & gas industry	Cool Planet Technologies, Ardent, Linde, Petronas	6-7	60-120
Cryogenic	post-combustion	Air Liquide, Linde	5-9	70-150
Solid Looping	post-combustion	SFW	5-7	50-60
Inherent Capture	oxy-combustion	CEOX, 8 Rivers	5-6+	-

*chemical and physical
**captured CO₂

According to Global CCS Institute (2025b), liquid absorption refers to the method of capturing CO₂ utilizing a liquid. The capturing can happen either chemically or physically. When CO₂ is chemically captured, it is bonded to the absorbing material by forming a new chemical compound in a reaction. Typically, the reaction is reversed by applying heat.

Physical liquid absorbents rely on the CO₂ dissolving into the absorption liquid, where the CO₂ is held by van der Waals forces. The CO₂ is released by rapidly lowering the pressure of the vessel resulting in a pressure swing, “flashing” the CO₂ back into gas. The same concepts are generally true for solid absorbents, where instead of using a liquid absorbing agent, a solid porous material is used. In physical solid absorption, instead of dissolving, the CO₂ is held in the molecular structure of the solid absorbent by van der Waals forces. Typically, in applications with lower CO₂ partial pressure, the more suitable option is chemical absorption, while for higher partial pressures, the more suitable option is physical absorption. Generally, at least two vessels are used to allow there to be one capturing vessel at all times. Liquid Absorption technologies are quite far in development. One of the most known carbon capture technologies that has reached commercial deployment is provided by SLB Capturi (Aker) and utilizes liquid absorption (Global CCS Institute, 2025a).

Membrane technologies involve a semi-permeable barrier or medium, which is utilized to separate desired chemicals from a mixture based on their transfer rates through the membrane from higher-pressure side to lower pressure side (Global CCS Institute, 2025b). The technology is widely utilized in the oil and gas industry in refining purposes. Providers and utilizers for the technology in CC purpose include for example Cool Planet Technologies and Linde (Global CCS Institute, 2025a).

Cryogenic CO₂ capture condenses CO₂ directly from a flue gas stream as CO₂ has a different condensation point than most other gases in flue gas streams (Global CCS Institute, 2025b). The gas process happens at low temperatures and at higher pressures to prevent the CO₂ from solidifying into dry ice. The technology has an advantage over other capture methods as the product CO₂ does not need much further processing since it is already in liquid form and relatively pure. Cryogenic CC has been investigated to cost approximately 70-150 USD/CO₂ captured (Hanson, et al. 2025). Providers include Air Liquide and Linde (Global CCS Institute, 2025a).

Solid looping relies on the same principles as chemical absorbent technologies, but instead of keeping the absorbent in the same vessel cycling between absorption and regeneration phases, separate vessels for each reaction are used with the absorbent circulating between them to facilitate continuous operation (Shimizu, et al. 1999). Solid looping technologies, such as CaL, which is described in detail in chapter 3 are generally at TRL 5-7. The costs of CaL have been estimated at approximately 50-60 USD/CO_{2captured} and as such is proposed

often as an affordable CC technology (De Lena, et al. 2019). Solid looping technologies are in development for example by SFW. (Global CCS Institute, 2025a).

Inherent capture processes are chemical process systems that naturally produce CO₂ as part of their operation, such as fermentation of ethanol and production of ethylene oxide (Global CCS Institute, 2025b). Producing ammonia by extracting CO₂ from the process stream of hydrogen also produces high pressure CO₂. Cement manufacturing companies are examining ways to increase the concentration of CO₂ in the gas released from calciners. The new methods keep the limestone separated from the heated gas and burners to keep the CO₂ from getting diluted by the burner air. The Allam-Fetvedt cycle, where a modified Brayton cycle is used to convert carbon fuels into energy while also capturing the generated CO₂, have also been proposed by for example 8 Rivers and CEOX.

3 Calcium Looping

CaL is a promising post-combustion CC technology that has been successfully demonstrated to be a viable option in reducing the CO₂ emissions from hard-to-abate industrial sectors. This chapter examines the fundamental concept of the CaL process and provides a more detailed overview of the driving chemical reaction as well as the main components of the system.

3.1 Process Overview

In their patent, Hirama et al. (1994) first proposed the idea of separating CO₂ from flue gases by feeding the gases through a cooled reactor where they react with a metal oxide sorbent to fix the CO₂ into a metal carbonate. The metal carbonate is then thermally decomposed in a separate reactor back into CO₂ and metal oxide, utilizing heat generated from fuel combustion. The resulting CO₂ gas is directed to post processing, and the metal oxide is circulated back into the first reactor thus completing the cycle.

The concept of using the reversible carbonation-calcination reaction of calcium oxide, expressed in Equation (1), to capture CO₂ from flue gases was proposed by Shimizu et al. (1999). The idea behind the concept is the same as the original patent in which Shimizu is also a co-author.

The carbonation reaction of CaO is exothermic releasing heat and has a reaction enthalpy of $\Delta H_0 = -178 \text{ kJ/mol}$ and respectively the calcination reaction of CaCO₃ is endothermic requiring heat. The chemical equilibrium is dependent on the temperature and the partial pressure of CO₂ in the process. As the partial pressure of CO₂ increases, the temperature required to shift the reaction balance towards calcination increases. Figure 8 shows that at approximately 900 °C the temperature is high enough to decompose CaCO₃ even when the surrounding gas contains pure CO₂ at atmospheric pressures.

Figure 8. Partial pressure curve of CO₂ in equilibrium with CaCO₃ and CaO (Stanmore, et al. 2005)

The equilibrium curve presented in Figure 8 is plotted using equation (2) which is based on a mathematical model for dispersed calcium carbonate. The equation is often cited to be developed by Silcox et al. (1989), but in this form, it is seen in the scientific article written by Stanmore et al. (2005). The equations are derived from the Gibbs free energy of reactions and thermochemical data found, for example in the book by Barin et al. (1989).

$$\frac{p_{eq,CO_2}}{p_\infty} = 4.137 \times 10^7 \times e^{\frac{-20474}{T}} \quad (2)$$

where p_{eq,CO_2} is the equilibrium partial pressure of CO₂ [Pa], p_∞ is atmospheric pressure and T is the prevailing temperature [K].

Similarly to the original patent by Hirama et al. (1994), the CaL process also utilizes two reactors as the reaction direction is dependent on the prevailing conditions (Shimizu, et al. 1999). The current state-of-the-art system consists of two interconnected Circulating Fluidized Bed (CFB) reactors, the carbonator (CB, absorber) and the calciner (CC, regenerator) which can be seen in Figure 9 (Shimizu, et al. 1999; Diego, et al. 2016).

Figure 9. Diagram of a basic CaL process

Flue gas (FG in figures, tables and equations) is fed into the carbonator, where it reacts exothermically with CaO fixing the CO₂ into CaCO₃ according to Equation (1). Flue gas depleted from CO₂ is released from the carbonator. The CaCO₃ is fed into the calciner, where the reverse endothermic reaction takes place, releasing CO₂-rich product gas (PG in figures, tables and equations). The resulting CaO is transferred back into the carbonator. The circulating sorbent consists mostly of CaO and in the optimal process the sorbent flowing from calciner towards the carbonator has minimal content of CaCO₃.

3.2 Carbonator and Calciner

Since the process utilizes the carbonation-calcination reaction of CaO, characteristics such as the optimal temperatures of the reactors are heavily dictated by the reaction kinetics and the chemical equilibrium. According to the current understanding, the optimal operation temperature for the carbonator is approximately 650 °C (Diego, et al. 2016).

To keep the temperatures at the optimal levels for the carbonation reaction, the carbonator reactor needs to be cooled as heat is brought into the reactor along with the high temperature solids from the calciner and released in the exothermic carbonation reaction. The heat can be effectively removed from the reactor using, for example, bayonet tubes equipped with circulating cooling water in pilot scale or membrane walls as typically seen in commercial-scale steam boilers.

Figure 10. Simplified figure of carbonator in CaL system

One parameter that determines the height of the CFB carbonator reactor is the residence time of the particles inside the reactor. The residence time is required to be long enough to reach the desired carbonation levels. As described in for example Alvares et al (2005), the carbonation proceeds in two distinct phases identifiable by the sudden and significant transition in reaction speed. In the first phase, rapid carbonation takes place where CO_2 molecules react directly with the exposed CaO molecules. The following phase is significantly slower, as CO_2 molecules diffuse through a CaCO_3 product layer that has formed around the CaO particles. The change in reaction speed happens when the product layer reaches approximately 50 nm.

The sorbent is transferred to the calciner side presented in Figure 11 via the transfer marked in both Figure 10 and Figure 11. Recycle, also marked in the figure, can direct a portion of the solids back into the reactor they originated from. The sorbent is separated from the output gases at each side of the system in a cyclone. Below each cyclone, loop seals (LS) are used to separate the lower pressures inside the cyclones from the higher pressures at the bottom of the reactors. In literature regarding CaL the solids streams are sometimes referred to as internal and external circulation. However, to avoid confusion with the different meaning they have in CFB literature, the terms “recycle”, and “transfer” are used throughout the work.

Figure 11. Simplified figure of a calciner in CaL system

Fuel combustion is required to supply the needed heat for the reverse, endothermic reaction taking place in the calciner. The temperature inside the calciner is controlled by altering the amount of fuel fed into the reactor. The optimal operating temperature for the calciner is approximately 900 °C (Diego, et al. 2016).

The calciner operates under oxy-combustion conditions with a mixture of recirculated flue gases and oxygen. Oxy-fuel combustion technique allows improved efficiency since energy is not used up to heat nitrogen (Markewitz, et al. 2012). This also results in a cleaner combustion and reduces the formation of nitrogen oxides and the overall nitrogen content in the CO₂-rich product gases of the calciner, making the post-processing of the gas simpler (Markewitz, et al. 2012).

A make-up feed of fresh limestone is required to maintain the desired CO₂ carrying capacity of the sorbent and therefore capture efficiency of the system. The carrying capacity decreases over time as sorbent is lost via deactivation with additional losses occurring as portion escapes the system as fly-ash (FA), depending on the sorbent type. A solids purge system is used to remove the deactivated sorbent and species such as ash and CaSO₄ from the system.

Figure 12. Sorbent carrying capacity

Sorbent deactivation or degradation occurs when the sorbent has cycled a number of times due to, for example, sintering of the porous CaO at high temperatures inside the calciner. Sintering is the process of the sorbent particles forming into solid larger particles. At high temperatures the calcination is rapid but quickly degrades the sorbent. A compromise temperature can be determined at which the reaction happens desirably fast but at the same time protecting the sorbent. Several publications examining the degradation or the “carrying capacity” of the sorbent have been made such as Abanades (2002) and Grasa & Rodriguez (2006), who combined the data from multiple limestones into a fitted curve. The curve is shown in Figure 12 and represents the evolution of carbonation conversion fraction over number of cycles. The curve is produced using equation (3), which is an equation for calculating the maximum carbonation conversion X at N number of circulations.

$$X_N = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{1 - X_r} + kN} + X_r \quad (3)$$

where X_r is the residual conversion capacity constant 0.075 and k is the deactivation constant 0.52, both of which show good relation to true limestone.

4 Methods for Pilot Plant Performance Evaluation

This chapter describes the methods utilized in the calculation tool and evaluation of the La Pereda pilot performance. Developing the tool used to obtain the KPIs is one of the main objectives of the thesis. The tool is designed to calculate relevant process parameters for specific time intervals or averaged periods. The chapter gives a description of how the calculation tool works and presents the data and process-oriented logic by visualizing them with flow charts. Additionally, the chapter expresses the equations used to complete the mass and heat balances as well as the equations for the KPIs, which are also described in detail. The implementation of the tool can be divided by their topic into two main parts. First part concerns the handling of the data, and the second part concerns the thermodynamic solving process.

4.1 Evaluation Tool Overview

The tool was built in Microsoft Excel, and it involves VBA programming language. Excel was chosen as the platform for developing the tool, as a spreadsheet offers a balance between visual and text-based interfaces. While visualizing the process is not the main purpose of the tool, the customizable visual environment provided by the spreadsheet allows for improved readability and usability over text-based tools such as MATLAB. Additionally, the involvement of VBA programming brings nearly infinite possibilities in terms of how the calculation routine is implemented and nearly competes with the usability of MATLAB code.

The approach allows a calculation worksheet to be built around a visual sketch representation of the CaL system. The measurement data can be therefore mapped to their respective places in the worksheet along with calculations and the resulting process parameters. The bulk of the calculations happen in this single worksheet and only calculations related to the stoichiometric combustion products of the fuel and calculations related to other initial values or to derived results happen on a separate worksheet.

The development of the tool was guided by the three main objectives that are as follows:

Relevance: The tool can be utilized to calculate relevant parameters related to the CaL process and the La Pereda pilot plant. The parameters are defined based on typical ones used in literature and other research as well as those relevant for process scale-up purposes.

Clarity: The tool is designed to be easy to use and understand, even for someone unfamiliar with it. The spreadsheet layout supports this by visually presenting the process and keeping the calculations in their respective locations. The results are shown on a separate worksheet to keep them organized.

Further Development: The tool is developed with future in mind. The expectation is that the tool can be used for scaling up purposes of the process. The tool is built with an aim to facilitate remapping of the measurement data in case the format of the measurement data changes.

4.2 Data Handling Logic

Instead of building the calculation tool to process all data at once in a large table, where each row is dedicated for a single data point and each column for a specific quantity, it was decided that the calculations would be performed individually for each data point. “Data point” refers to one row of input data containing all measurements taken at that specific time. In this approach the data points are extracted from the data using a combination of VBA subroutines and Excel worksheet functions. Data is then fed through the calculation process where results are produced. The reason behind this approach is to maintain the readability and clarity of the tool.

The main worksheet named “Chart” contains the mentioned visual representation of the process and the bulk of the calculations. The top part of this worksheet has information on which data point is currently active on the worksheet and controls for choosing other data points. These are the main controls used to select and perform the calculations.

It is possible to import any data into the tool by adding it as a new worksheet and then adding the name of the worksheet to the datasheet list. The data can then be selected from a drop-down menu. The imported measurement data must follow a certain format. However, only a remapping of the measurements to the calculation is required if a change in format were to happen as long as the date and time column remains the same.

A flow chart of the simplified idea behind the data handling logic is presented in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Flow chart of the simplified data handling

The selection of the calculation type is an intermediary step in the data handling. When a worksheet name is picked from the drop-down menu, the respective data is moved to “selected data” worksheet. Solids sample data is also moved from a separate solids sample data table and interpolated to match the measurement interval of the main measurement data. At this point, if the user decides that the calculation is to be performed on the raw data, per single data point, the data is moved as it is to the “handled data” worksheet. If the user decides to perform the calculation with single averaged values of a specific interval, the raw data is used to calculate the average, which is placed at the top of the “handled data” worksheet. If the user decides to perform the calculation with periodically averaged values, the averaging is performed using the user selected interval. After each average is calculated, the result is moved to the “handled data” worksheet.

The user can then choose to either calculate a single data row by its index number, manually step forwards or backwards a chosen number of rows using specific buttons in the calculation worksheet, or to automatically calculate all the rows that are available in the currently

selected data. In every procedure the active row is fetched from the “handled data” worksheet using the worksheet functions INDEX and MATCH according to a row indicator number that is set by the corresponding VBA subroutine of the calculation procedure.

The calculated results are extracted from the calculations worksheet into a separate results table on another worksheet to maintain a structured and clear approach. This is only in effect when the “update results” tick-box is selected. The purpose of the result worksheet is to also function as the main results page for single data points or single averages. For cases where multiple data points are processed, a combination of VBA subroutines and worksheet functions is used to fill a table on another worksheet with the results, where each row corresponds to a specific time interval. The table can then be used for figure creation.

4.3 Solving of Process Parameters

The solving process is presented in Figure 14 as a flow chart to illustrate how the tool calculates the process parameters. Figure 14 represents the “CALCULATION” block shown in Figure 13. The blocks written in capital letters are examined closer with a flow chart in the following subchapters.

Figure 14. Solving process flow chart

The solving process first calculates the values derived directly from the data. The following steps are used to estimate the flow rates and compositions of the gases exiting the reactors. Next, the solids transfer rates are calculated based on the energy balances. After the calculation of the solids transfer rates, if the previously calculated values do not match, an iteration will take place until the accuracy or maximum iteration criteria are reached. Finally, the values derived from the results are calculated, this includes the KPIs as well as other important parameters. The user can choose the way to calculate calcination in the calciner as well as which heat balance is used for the calculation of solids transfer rate.

4.3.1 Assumptions and Data Derived Values

To aid the calculation process and to keep it on a reasonable level while maintaining accurate enough results for the purpose of this thesis, a set of assumptions was determined. Altogether, there are 14 assumptions, which are the following.

1. **Ambient air:** Ambient air is assumed to be composed of 21 % O₂, 78 % N₂ and 1 % Argon (Ar), at a temperature of 20 °C. Other gases such as CO₂ present in the atmosphere are not considered due to their insignificant fraction.
2. **Ash:** The thermochemical properties, such as molar mass and specific heat capacity of SiO₂ are used to represent the ash. The circulating solids are assumed to contain a steady 10 % ash on a weight basis.
3. **Burner cooling air:** The airflow from the separate cooling fan through the start-up burners for both reactors is considered to be shut off during operation. This cooling air is assumed to be ambient air. In turn, a portion of the gas that is flowing through the grid into the reactors is directed through the burners to act as cooling.
4. **Combustion inside carbonator:** When consumption of O₂ is observed in the carbonator, it is assumed to be caused by the combustion of residual char that is carried over from the calciner.
5. **Cooling bayonets:** The inlet temperature of the cooling water circulating in the cooling bayonets stays at a constant 14 °C regardless of other conditions.

- 6. Escaping solids:** Since bottom ash removal system is not considered as it was not in operation during the tests, the mass flow of solids escaping through the cyclones as FA is assumed to be equal to the input mass flow of the calcined make-up limestone and the ash content of fuel. Three quarters of the escaping solids exit through the calciner cyclone, while the rest exit through the carbonator cyclone. For the calculation of individual data points, this introduces error, since the calculation does not consider the residence time of the particles and instead uses the mass flow rate at each specific moment.
- 7. Heat loss:** The total heat losses are assumed to be split between the carbonator and the calciner. The split used is 40 % for the carbonator and 60 % for the calciner. The heat loss is calculated from the overall heat balance of the whole system. The heat that is transferred through the walls of the cyclone, standpipe and loop seals are considered to fall under this value and therefore do not have heat loss values of their own.
- 8. Ideal gas assumption:** All gases are assumed to behave as ideal gases. Therefore, molar and volume fractions are considered to be equal.
- 9. Linearly interpolated sample analysis data:** As the frequency of the sample analysis differs from that of the other measurements, linear interpolation is used to fill in the gaps and smooth out the changes in the solids composition between the data points.
- 10. LS fluidization gas flow share:** It is assumed that 5 % of the loop seal fluidization gas escapes through the cyclone while the remaining share flows to the respective reactor along with the solids transfer stream.
- 11. N₂:** Since the concentration of nitrogen was not measured anywhere, it is assumed that the fraction of the gas that is unaccounted for in the measurements at both the inlets and outlets is nitrogen.
- 12. No solids recycle:** For the whole duration of the tests, the solids recycling, was disabled in both reactors.
- 13. NO_x ratio:** Plant measurements do not specify the ratio of NO to NO₂. Therefore, in cases where FTIR measurements are not available for the specific experiment, the

ratio is calculated using averaged values from an experiment with FTIR measurements.

14. Reference temperature: A reference temperature of 20 °C is used for all heat flow calculations.

Several key parameters are calculated or derived from the available measurements, including gas and solids compositions, inlet gas flow rates, solids inventory estimates, fuel properties, and cooling duty. The parameters are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Measured and data derived parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Units
temperatures	T	°C
pressures	p	bar, Pa
measured flow rates	\dot{V} & \dot{m}	m ³ /s, kg/s
solids inventory	W	kg
solids carbonate molar content	X	-
cooling	Q_{cool}	kW

Most of the flow rate measurements are already converted to either volumetric flow rate or mass flow rate. However, some venturi measurements need to be converted from direct pressure values into flow rates. Possible correction of venturis is also taken into account. At inlets, gas composition measurements are used to calculate the share of N₂ and Ar according to assumptions 1 and 11, as well as the species specific molar flow rates.

All gas composition measurements are taken as dry volumetric measurements, which give the concentration of the gas species as if the gas contained no water. The dry measurements need to be converted into wet readings to be able to accurately determine the species-specific flow rates. The conversion to wet readings requires the water content to be known and is performed according to equation (4). The calculation of water content is described in the next subchapter, 4.3.2

$$c_{i,\text{wet}} = c_{i,\text{dry}} (1 - c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}) \quad (4)$$

where c presents the molar concentrations of a gas species i in wet and dry concentrations and $c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ represents the water molar concentration in the gas. All concentrations can be given as volumetric or molar according to assumption no. 8.

The inventory of solids W [kg] inside the reactors can be estimated from the pressure drop between the bottom of the reactor and the top of the reactor utilizing equation (5) (Youn, et al. 2022).

$$W = A \frac{\Delta p}{g} \quad (5)$$

where Δp is the change in pressure [Pa] over the height of the reactor, A is the cross-sectional area [m²] of the reactor and g is the gravitational acceleration [m²/s]. Moreover, dividing the resulting value with A gives the specific solids inventory W_s of the reactor which can be useful for comparison of different plants.

The solids sample analysis provides the carbon (C) and sulphur (S) content by weight of the circulating solids. The ash content of the circulating solids is assumed to be 10 % according to assumption no. 2. With the C, S and ash contents, the percentage of the main circulating solids species, CaO, CaCO₃ and CaSO₄ can be determined. CaCO₃ contains carbon, which means that the measured percentage of carbon can be assumed to originate from the CaCO₃. Char particles are avoided in the samples. Therefore, the percentage of CaCO₃ can be determined by multiplying the ratio of molar masses of CaCO₃ and C with the measured percentage of C. Similarly, the percentage of CaSO₄ can be determined by multiplying the ratio of molar masses of CaSO₄ and S with the measured percentage of S. Finally, the percentage of CaO can be determined by assuming it to be the remaining share after CaCO₃, CaSO₄ and ash. The calcination percentage can be estimated using the solids sample analysis. The calcination percentage indicates how much of the available CaCO₃ breaks down into CaO and CO₂ inside the calciner.

Fuel combustion products and stoichiometric oxygen consumption are calculated according to the balanced reaction equations for combustion of C, hydrogen (H) and S based on the ultimate composition analysis of the fuel. A pre-determined heating value of 19.4 MJ_{LHV,dry}/kg is used, and it is not calculated from the combustion reactions.

The cooling duty of the cooling bayonets can be calculated directly from the measurement data as the flow rate along with both inlet and outlet temperatures of the cooling water were measured. The cooling duty Q_{cool} [kW] can be calculated using Equation (6).

$$Q_{\text{cool}} = \dot{m}_{\text{cool}}(h_2 - h_1) \quad (6)$$

where \dot{m} is the mass flow rate of water [kg/s], h is the specific enthalpy of the cooling water [kJ/kg] at bayonet inlets, 1, and at bayonet outlets, 2.

4.3.2 Calculation of Process Parameters and Completion of Balances

The main part of the solving process includes the solving of the parameters listed in Table 4, of which the most crucial ones are the obtaining of outlet flow rates, and the calculation of the solids transfer mass flows. These parameters are required to complete the material and heat balances of the system.

Table 4. Calculated parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Unit
outlet gas flow rates	FG, in & PG	mol/s, kg/s
burnt biomass	-	mol/s, kg/s
emissions	-	ppm, mg/MJ _{LHV}
solids transfer mass flows	\dot{m}_{toCB} & \dot{m}_{toCC}	kg/s
material balances	-	kg/s, %
heat balances	-	kW, %

The gas phase flow rates at the reactor outlets $\dot{m}_{\text{FG,out}}$ and \dot{m}_{PG} can be calculated based on the flow rate measurements at the inlets of the reactors, reaction stoichiometry and composition measurements at the outlets. The reactions taking place in both reactors lead to changes in species-specific flow rates and therefore the gas compositions. The calculation must take these changes into account. Composition measurements at the reactor outlets can be assumed to be relatively accurate, therefore they can be used in estimating the changes due to reactions. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements were also taken at certain locations of the system at certain time intervals. The FTIR measurement gives the wet molar concentrations of gas species and provides accurate composition information even at low concentrations and does not need calibration. Iteration is required in the calculation, since the flow rate of the outlet gases change depending on the reactions inside, the calculations of which, in turn, depend on the outlet flow rates.

Based on these factors, an iterative method for calculating the outlet flows for both reactors was chosen. The method is presented in the following flow chart (Figure 15). The figure includes the calculation routine of the outlet gas flows for both of the reactors. Figure 15 refers to the “ITERATE CB OUTLET” and “ITERATE CC OUTLET” seen in Figure 14.

Figure 15. Reactor outlet gas flow calculation process, left side for carbonator and right side for calciner

According to Figure 14, the carbonator side is calculated first. This starts by calculating the total gas molar flow rate “FG,out” at the carbonator outlet using the volumetric wet percentage and the molar flow rate of N₂. The percentage is derived from the measurement data according to assumption no. 11 and the calculated water content at the carbonator outlet. The molar flow rate of N₂ at the carbonator outlet is determined as the sum of all N₂ flows into the carbonator side. As per assumption no. 8, volumetric and molar percentages are interchangeable. The molar flow rate at the reactor outlet, \dot{n}_{outlet} [mol/s], forms into equation (7) which stands true for both reactors:

$$\dot{n}_{\text{outlet}} = \frac{\dot{n}_i}{c_{i,\text{wet}}} \quad (7)$$

where \dot{n} is the molar flow rate [mol/s] of gas at the outlet of the reactor. The flow rate can then be used with the measurement data to obtain the molar flow rates of individual gas species and with molar mass of the gas, the mass flow rate of the gas.

Together with the inlet and outlet flow rates of individual gas species, it is possible to determine changes inside the reactor. Using the changes, the consumption of O₂ is calculated. The change in O₂ inside carbonator is assumed to happen due to combustion of char as per assumption no. 4. This produces CO₂ as a product which alters the outlet composition. Since the change is dependent on the outlet composition and the outlet composition is dependent on the change, a VBA subroutine is used to iterate the O₂ consumption to obtain a value for O₂ consumption that completes the O₂ balance inside the carbonator. The same procedure is used to determine the rate of carbonation. Since carbonation alters the gas composition, in a case where the composition changes notably, the iteration routine is started from beginning.

On the calciner side the calculation method of the outlet gas flow “PG” is determined by the combustion mode of the reactor as the pilot can be operated using air or simulated recirculated flue gases. In air-combustion mode, the concentration of N₂ is used. However, in normal operation, oxy-combustion mode, the concentration of CO₂ in the product gases is used instead. The fuel combustion can be calculated either from the O₂ consumption or from the fuel mass flow rate determined as the difference between the total fuel input into the system and the amount consumed in the carbonator. The calcination percentage is calculated as a ratio between calcinated CaCO₃ calculated according to the sample analysis and total CaCO₃ input to the reactor.

Emissions are already measured as volumetric percentages of dry gas at the outlets, which are converted into wet readings according to equation (4). The FTIR analyser was located at the calciner outlet in some experiments. In those certain experiments, the composition measurements provided by the FTIR are used to give more accurate readings of the low concentrations of the emissive species. An important parameter that ties the emissions to the amount of fuel burned, and therefore to the thermal power of the CaL plant, is the emission intensity [mg/MJ]. As the mass flow rates of the emissive gas species, CO and NO_x, and

fuel consumption are determined, the specific emissions can be obtained by dividing the flow rates by the fuel power.

The solids transfer rate is calculated using four main methods, which utilize different regions of the system. The user can pick which method to use. The obtained transfer rates also complete the energy balances for the regions and the system. The four methods used are the following:

1. The heat balance of the entire carbonator side CFB hot loop.
2. The heat balance of the carbonator side loop seal.
3. The heat balance of the entire calciner side CFB hot loop.
4. The heat balance of the calciner side loop seal.

According to assumption 14, all heat flows are calculated with a reference temperature of 20 °C. Material and heat balance calculations of the CaL process require thorough balancing of each individual reactor system.

The equation used to calculate the mass flow rate of the circulating solids is presented in equation (8). The same equation can be implemented for all the methods of transfer rate calculation. In the equation, the resulting $\dot{m}_{\text{transfer}}$, represents the transfer rate of solids arriving to the control volume.

$$\dot{m}_{\text{transfer}} = \frac{\sum Q_{\text{sources}} - \sum Q_{\text{sinks}}}{(h_2 - h_1)} \quad (8)$$

where Q_{sources} represents the heat flows of all source terms except for the solids transfer in, Q_{sinks} represents the heat flows all of the sink terms except for the solids transfer out, h_1 is the specific enthalpy [kJ/kg] of the solids at inlet and h_2 is the specific enthalpy [kJ/kg] of the solids at outlet. In the case of the carbonator and the calciner, the mass flow rates of solids entering and leaving the control volume differ due to the transfer of mass between the solid and gas phases caused by chemical reactions. The material stream leaving the control volume is therefore calculated by taking the reactions into account.

The most accurate method, in terms of the number of variables, is to calculate the transfer rate using the heat balance that considers only the loop seal on the carbonator side. On the contrary, since reactor balances have more variables, the deviation in a single variable will

not affect the result as much as in the balances of the loop seals. Figure 16 shows the material and heat balance diagram for the carbonator side loop seal.

Figure 16. Carbonator side loop seal material and heat balance

The balance of the carbonator loop seal includes the material and heat flows in and out of the loop seal. Heat losses are not taken into account here. According to assumption no. 12, solids recycling is also not considered. In the diagram “s” represents the solid phase and “g” represents the gas phase. “LS” on the other hand, represents the gas stream used to fluidize the loop seal. “toCC” indicates that the flow is going towards the calciner. The solids flow in and out of the loop seal are equal, and it is the resulting solids transfer rate.

Figure 17. Carbonator side material and heat balance

The second method is to calculate the transfer rate using the heat balance of the carbonator CFB hot loop. The material and heat balance diagram of the carbonator side is shown in Figure 17. Compared to calculating the transfer using the loop seal heat balances, the calculation using reactor heat balances requires many more variables such as heat produced from reactions. The amount of heat created by the carbonation reaction marked with “carb” is calculated from the reaction enthalpy of carbonation of CaO as seen in equation (1). “comb” on the carbonator side indicates the heat from the combustion of char according to assumption no. 4. Here the heat losses are also taken into account. “toCB” refers to the flows that are going from the calciner to the carbonator. Escaping solids marked with “FA” are calculated according to assumption no. 6. Part of the flue gases are directed through the start-up burner on the side of the riser to act as cooling for the burner which does not have an effect on the calculation during normal operation.

Figure 18. Calciner side material and heat balance

The third method is to calculate the transfer using the heat balance of the calciner CFB hot loop. The material and heat balance diagram of the calciner side is shown in Figure 18. Since largely all fuel fed into the system is combusted inside the calciner and the heating value of the fuel being quite high, small variations in fuel flow measurements cause large variations in the calculated combustion heat. This causes observable variations in the transfer rate results. A significant amount of heat is consumed by the calcination reaction, marked with

“calc”. It is highly dependent on the make-up feed flow rate measurement. These are the main reasons for the inaccuracies of the calciner side material and heat balances. Similarly to the carbonator side, a portion of the oxidant is directed through the start-up burner in the side of the riser to act as cooling, which again does not have an effect on the calculation during normal operation.

The energy balance of the calciner side loop seal is the most uncertain since there is combustion and calcination taking place inside the loop seal and there are no measurements that could be utilized to confirm the extent of either one. However, it is safe to assume that most of the remaining unburned fuel or char leaving the calciner would combust inside the calciner loop seal given the high temperature and oxygen rich environment caused by the fluidization air. The material and heat balance diagram of the calciner loop seal is shown in Figure 19. The figure contains the material and heat flows in and out of the carbonator side loop seal as well as the heat created and consumed by the potential combustion of char and calcination. Possible heat loss is not taken into account here.

Figure 19. Calciner side loop seal material and heat balance

The overall material and heat balances of the whole CaL system are presented in Figure 20. The overall heat balance is used to calculate the heat losses according to assumption no. 7. Calculating the heat losses from the difference in the overall heat balance can also be considered as determining the heat transfer to the refractory wall. Therefore, due to the calculation method, during rapid cooling of the reactors, the heat loss calculation will return a negative value indicating heat transfer from the walls back into the reactor, effectively turning the sink term of heat loss into a source term.

Figure 20. Overall material and heat balance

After the transfer rates have been determined, the values are moved to different cells with VBA subroutines, where they can be utilized for the next calculation round. At this point, the material and heat balances of the systems can be closed, since all other variables are already known. The following equations are true for all of the balances above:

$$\sum \dot{m}_{\text{source}} = \sum \dot{m}_{\text{sink}} \quad (9)$$

$$\sum Q_{\text{source}} = \sum Q_{\text{sink}} \quad (10)$$

The equations (9) and (10) represent the generalized completed material and heat balances for a system in a steady state, where the source and sink terms of material and heat are equal. An imbalance of either term indicates that the energy or material stored inside the system changes.

4.4 Key Performance Indicators

KPIs are tools that are used to evaluate the operation and performance of various topics. KPIs are not limited to industrial applications but can also measure social or other metrics. However, as this thesis is related to engineering, the KPIs used and discussed are in the context of industrial applications.

KPIs in industry are often used as metrics of how a process or a plant operates. In pilot testing, they are important metrics as they directly show if the design that is being tested is operating as intended. Typical KPIs that are used in evaluating the performance of a CaL process are listed in Table 5 with more detailed descriptions below. The KPIs are chosen based on previous literature and research such as Haaf et al (2020), Ströhle et al (2020) and Diego et al. (2020). This chapter will focus on describing the KPIs derived from the results of the solving process in more detail. Descriptions of the other parameters can be found in previous chapters.

Table 5. Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Symbol	Units
carbonator efficiency	E_{carb}	%
calciner efficiency	E_{calc}	%
total CO ₂ capture efficiency	E_{tot}	%
solids transfer ratio	Φ	mol _{CaO} /mol _{CO₂}
make-up ratio	Λ	mol _{CaCO₃} /mol _{CO₂}
average maximum CO ₂ carrying capacity	X_{ave}	%
specific solids transfer rate	$G_{\text{s,carb}}$ & $G_{\text{s,calc}}$	kg/(m ² s)
superficial gas velocities	u_{grid} & u_{top}	m/s
excess oxygen factor	λ	-
origin of CO ₂ in PG	-	%, kg/s

Carbonator Efficiency

Carbonator efficiency E_{carb} is a metric that indicates the efficiency at which CO₂ is captured by the sorbent inside the carbonator. The efficiency is limited by the prevailing temperature inside the reactor as the chemical equilibrium concentration of CO₂ presented in Figure 8 is temperature dependent. E_{carb} is calculated from the ratio of captured CO₂ and the amount of CO₂ fed into the carbonator as follows in equation (6):

$$E_{\text{carb}} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{FG},\text{in}} - \dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{FG},\text{out}}}{\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{FG},\text{in}}} \quad (11)$$

where $F_{\text{CO}_2,\text{FG},\text{in}}$ is the molar flow rate [mol/s] of CO₂ flowing into the carbonator as part of the flue gases and $F_{\text{CO}_2,\text{FG},\text{out}}$ is the molar flow rate of CO₂ in the flue gases leaving the carbonator.

Calclner Efficiency

Calclner efficiency E_{calc} is a similar metric to E_{carb} . It is an indicator of how much of the total entering CaCO_3 calcinates in the calciner. It can be calculated as the ratio of moles of CaCO_3 calcined and moles of CaCO_3 entering the calciner. It is expressed as equation (12):

$$E_{\text{calc}} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{CaO}}(X_{\text{carb}} - X_{\text{calc}}) + \dot{n}_{\text{CaCO}_3,0}(1 - X_{\text{calc}})}{\dot{n}_{\text{CaCO}_3,\text{R}} + \dot{n}_{\text{CaCO}_3,0}} \quad (12)$$

where X_{calc} is the molar carbonate content in the solids leaving the calciner, X_{carb} is the molar carbonate content in the solids arriving at the calciner, \dot{n}_{CaO} is the molar flow of CaO into the carbonator $\dot{n}_{\text{CaCO}_3,0}$ is the fresh make-up limestone, and $\dot{n}_{\text{CaCO}_3,\text{R}}$ is limestone arriving to the calciner from the carbonator.

Total CO₂ Capture Efficiency

The total CO₂ capture efficiency E_{tot} indicates how much of the total CO₂ introduced to the system is present in the product gases at the calciner outlet. In its most basic form, it can be calculated according to equation (13):

$$E_{\text{tot}} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{PG}}}{\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{FG,in}} + \dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,0} + \dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{fuel}}} \quad (13)$$

where $\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{PG}}$ is the molar flow rate of CO₂ at the outlet of the calciner, $\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,0}$ is the molar flow rate of the CO₂ released in the first calcination of the make-up limestone and $\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{fuel}}$ is the molar flow of the CO₂ that is released in the combustion of the fuel. In oxy-combustion operation, the CO₂ that is fed into the calciner alongside the O₂ in the oxidant causes E_{tot} to increase unless it is taken into account as part of the incoming CO₂ flows. This is especially present when the CO₂ concentration in the primary gas is high as it is the case in the La Pereda experiments, where the recirculation of flue gases of the parent plant is simulated using a CO₂ feed from a tank. A characteristic of the process is that since CO₂ is formed in the calciner in both the calcination of make-up limestone and in the combustion of the fuel, the total CO₂ capture efficiency will always be higher than the efficiency of the carbonator.

Solids Transfer Ratio

Solids transfer ratio Φ [$\text{mol}_{\text{CaO}}/\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}$] is the ratio between the CaO flowing into the carbonator and the amount of CO₂ fed into the carbonator. The resulting ratio indicates how

much CaO is available for possible carbonation reaction in comparison to the amount of CO₂ fed into the reactor. It is defined according to equation (14):

$$\Phi = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{CaO}}}{\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{FG}, \text{in}}} \quad (14)$$

where \dot{n}_{CaO} is the molar flow rate of CaO into the carbonator.

Make-up Ratio

Make-up ratio Λ [$\text{mol}_{\text{CaCO}_3}/\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}$] (sometimes *MUR*) is the ratio between the flow of make-up limestone fed into the process and the flow of CO₂ fed into the carbonator. It indicates the share of CO₂ in the system that originates from the make-up flow, compared to that from the flue gas flow. It is defined as follows in equation (15):

$$\Lambda = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{CaCO}_3, 0}}{\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{FG}, \text{in}}} \quad (15)$$

Note that this value excludes the CO₂ fed alongside the oxy-combustion oxidant. The more detailed shares of the origins of the CO₂ in the system are presented in the material balance following chapters.

Average maximum CO₂ carrying capacity

The average maximum CO₂ carrying capacity X_{ave} indicates the extent to which the CaO sorbent inside a fully mixed carbonator reactor can react into CaCO₃. Since the CaL system is a loop, the circulating sorbent consists of particles that have circulated different number of times. To obtain the mass ratio r of the solid particles that have circulated N number of times through the system, equation (16) can be used (Abanades 2002).

$$r_N = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{CaO}, 0} \dot{n}_{\text{CaO}}^{N-1}}{(\dot{n}_{\text{CaO}, 0} + \dot{n}_{\text{CaO}})^N} \quad (16)$$

where $\dot{n}_{\text{CaO}, 0}$ is the molar flow [mol/s] of CaO from the calcined make-up. Note that if FA is considered, part of the fresh CaO will be lost. By combining equations (3) and (16), X_{ave} can be calculated according to equation (17).

$$X_{\text{ave}} = \sum_{N=1}^{N=\infty} r_N X_N \quad (17)$$

The method presented here requires there to be a constant measured value of the make-up flow into the system and provides best values when the system is at steady state.

Specific Solids Transfer Rate

Derived from the solids transfer mass flow rates \dot{m}_{toCB} and \dot{m}_{toCC} between the reactors calculated in chapter 4.3.2 the specific solids transfer rate G_s [kg/(m²s)] includes a dimensional aspect, the cross-sectional area of the reactors. It is calculated using equation (18):

$$G_s = \frac{\dot{m}}{A} \quad (18)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area of the reactor [m²] and \dot{m} is the circulating mass flow rate [kg/s] at the top of the reactor. The mass flow used here is the mass flow that exits the reactor, FA still considered.

Superficial Gas Velocities

Superficial gas velocities u_{grid} and u_{top} are also variables that are related to the dimensions of the reactors. The grid velocity is the velocity of the gas at the bottom of the reactors, where only the fluidization gases are considered. The top velocities are at the top of the reactors where all the gases that leave the reactor riser are considered. The flow velocity is determined by the design of the reactor and the minimum fluidization velocity, which is a very important parameter in CFB boilers, however, it is outside the scope of this work. The velocities are calculated using the volumetric flow rate of the gases adjusted to the correct volume according to the ideal gas law stating that volume is directly proportional to temperature when pressure is constant. The superficial gas velocity u [m/s] is therefore defined as shown in equation (19):

$$u = \frac{T}{T_{\text{ref}}} \frac{\dot{V}}{A} \quad (19)$$

where T is the prevailing temperature [K] at the location, T_{ref} is the reference temperature [K] and \dot{V} is the volumetric flow rate of the gas [m³/s].

Excess Oxygen Factor

The excess oxygen factor λ is a typical indicator for nearly every thermodynamic system involving combustion of any sort. It describes the amount of available oxygen in comparison to the amount of oxygen required for a full stoichiometric combustion. λ [-] can be expressed as equation (20):

$$\lambda = \frac{O_{2,\text{available}}}{O_{2,\text{required}}} \quad (20)$$

where $O_{2,\text{available}}$ is the total O_2 fed into the calciner and $O_{2,\text{required}}$ is the stoichiometric amount of O_2 required for the combustion of fuel.

Origin of CO_2 in Product Gas

The values show the origin, share, and flow rates of CO_2 in the product gas, indicating for example how much of the total CO_2 comes from the make-up stream or from the flue gases. This helps to better understand the meaning of the efficiency of the system.

4.5 Validation Methods

To confirm that the tool gives reasonable values, a set of validation calculations was used. The main validation method used across the different calculations is comparing the result to the result produced by a different calculation method.

The gas phase outlet flows of both reactors are calculated in two ways, first by using measurement data as described in chapter 4.3.1 . The second calculation method is performed using purely the material balance, meaning that the method calculates the outlet flow based on all in-going material and reactions that effect the gas phase. The gas compositions obtained from both methods are also compared with each other. The possible differences between the methods can also be seen in the species-specific material balance, since the method used to obtain the final results is based on the measured values. The capturing of the CO_2 is confirmed by comparing the captured amount calculated from the CO_2 balance of the carbonator to the captured amount calculate from the calculated transfer rate and the measured carbonate content.

The solids transfer rate calculation is validated by comparing the results of the four transfer rate calculation methods as well as the completed material and heat balances, all of which are described in chapter 4.3.2 . If a transfer rate differs greatly from the other methods, it is likely that there is something wrong. The calculated composition of solids is also used to verify the transfer rate. The composition is compared to the measured value and to a value that is calculated once-through along the circulation path of the process, taking into account all reactions that change the composition as well as the FA. The composition and transfer rates that are returned from the calculation can be used to estimate the accuracy of the transfer rates, reactions as well as the FA.

5 Performance Evaluation

The obtained results provide a deep look into the characteristics of the CaL process and the La Pereda pilot plant. The most important results can already be found in literature, along with detailed evaluations of their meaning. While the results produced in the work itself are not necessarily new, the way in which the tool allows for easy generation of these results could be considered as the main new result of the work.

The chapter starts with an overview of the test periods that presents the most important measured parameters as timeseries. The other subchapters present the various parameters as figures and tables and discuss their meaning. The final section also provides a more detailed look into some of the KPIs.

5.1 Overview of Test Periods

The test periods are certain intervals taken from the longer experiments. Each of the test periods has some characteristic feature such as temperature or limestone type. This work focuses on test periods 1 and 2, for which the full-length figures are based on 10-minute averaged values. The periods were chosen as they provide a good example of the system in a steady state. The specific test periods are marked in the figures as the clear parts, while the measurements outside the test periods are greyed out. For the test periods, averaged values are also provided. Figure 21 presents the measured temperatures from the reactor risers, fuel and make-up mass flow rates and the pressure difference between the tops and the bottoms of the reactor risers.

Figure 21a presents the four temperature measurements taken from both risers at different heights (except for the lower section of the carbonator where two measurements are taken at the same height). The difference between the temperatures of the carbonator and the calciner can be easily seen in the figure. It is also evident that the temperature of the calciner riser remains nearly the same above the height of 3.92 m. During the test periods, the temperatures of both risers remain relatively the same at height-weighted averages of approximately 587 °C for carbonator and 916 °C for calciner for period 1 and 589 °C and 921 °C for period 2 respectively.

Figure 21. Carbonator and calciner riser temperatures (a), fuel & make-up mass flow rates (b), and pressure delta over reactor risers (c)

Figure 21b presents the mass flow rates of the fuel feed and the make-up limestone feed. Refractory heating is visible in the elevated fuel flow at the beginning of the chart. More fuel is required to keep the temperatures of the reactor at the desired levels and over time as the temperature of the refractory catches, up the fuel requirement decreases. Make-up flow is

quite steady as a constant flow is required to counter the loss of solids and keep the solids inventory at the desired level.

The pressure change presented in Figure 21c can be utilized to calculate the solids inventory at the location of the pressure delta according to equation (5). The pressure change over the carbonator riser stays relatively the same over the whole duration, however on the calciner side the pressure change has a slight upwards trend over the whole period. This might indicate for example accumulation of inactive sorbent and ash.

Figure 22. Solids sample analysis values

The solids sample analysis values are shown in Figure 22. The samples were taken at four locations at an interval of approximately 45 minutes. The samples shown in the figure are calculated from the ultimate analysis values using the method described in chapter 4.3.1. During stable operation, samples taken from the carbonator side have always a higher content of CaCO_3 .

5.2 Material and Heat Balances

The heat balances of the carbonator and calciner sides and the whole system are presented in Figure 23 for the whole duration of the experiment day with the test periods highlighted. The figures separate the sources and sinks with their names that follow the previously

specified ones. The averages over the test periods are shown in separate tables. To obtain the results, the heat balance of the carbonator side was used.

Figure 23. Heat balances over time for carbonator side (a), calciner side (b), and overall system (c)

The heat balance of the carbonator side is presented in Figure 23a. From the figure it is clear that the largest source of heat in the carbonator is the solids transfer flow coming from the calciner. The second largest source is carbonation as expected from the system characteristics. The largest sink is the solids transfer toward the calciner with the second largest sink being cooling duty, which keeps the temperatures at the correct levels as designed and as previously discussed. Worth noting is the visibly higher heat loss at the beginning of the figure outside the test periods. The overall balance, shown as a red line, is very accurate, remaining at under 2 % difference compared to the smaller value.

Table 6. Carbonator heat balances for averaged periods

Sources/Sinks	Description	Heat [kW]	
		Period 1	Period 2
Sources	comb,CB	59.9	59.9
	carb	234	236
	FG,in	4.16	6.67
	burner	0.35	0.56
	LS,CB	0.0	0.0
	g,toCB	94.5	95.5
	s,toCB	901	884
	Total	1294	1282
Sinks	FG,out	249	252
	cool	376	409
	g,toCC	43.2	46.5
	s,toCC	529	521
	loss,CB	109.8	66.5
	FA,CB	8.3	8.5
		Total	1315
Balance	kW	-21.2	-21.7
	%	-1.64	-1.70

The averages of the test periods shown in Table 6 are very similar together, with the largest difference seen in the losses. The table indicates the same heat flows as Figure 23a with the addition of the loop seal fluidization air which remains at zero as it is at the ambient temperature of 20 °C. The error stays at approximately 2 % in both periods.

Figure 23a shows a spike in the ending which can also be seen in Figure 23b slightly less clearly. The spike is mostly caused by the heightened solids transfer heat flow, which is likely an artifact originating from the calculation method. It is caused by the rapid drop in the temperature of the calciner as fuel flow is cut, which leads to the total heat balance shifting negative, which in turn causes the calculated heat losses to rapidly increase. As the solids transfer rate calculation depends on the heat balances, it returns a higher transfer rate

that brings enough heat in to match the higher losses. Interestingly, the same increase can be seen in the solids transfer rate calculated by the energy balance of the loop seals shown in Figure 27 which are not affected by the heat losses. This indicates that the spike in the transfer rates is caused by the temperatures.

Table 7. Calciner heat balances for averaged periods

Sources/Sinks	Description	Heat [kW]	
		Period 1	Period 2
Sources	comb,CC	1908	1755
	oxidant	2.5	4.1
	burner	0.10	0.16
	LS,CC	0.0	0.0
	g,toCC	43.2	46.5
	s,toCC	529	521
	make-up	0.0	0.0
	fuel sensible	0.0	0.0
	Total	2483	2326
Sinks	PG	934	893
	calc	325	290
	g,toCB	94.5	95.5
	s,toCC	901	884
	loss,CC	164.7	99.7
	FA,CC	42.1	43.1
		Total	2462
Balance	kW	21.2	21.7
	%	0.85	0.93

On the calciner side presented in Figure 23b, by far the largest heat source is fuel combustion as expected. The second largest source is the solids transfer flow coming from the carbonator. The solids transfer out of the calciner side competes with the rich gas exiting the cyclone as the largest heat sinks. Calcination is also a significant part of the heat sinks. The balance of the calciner side is a maximum of 1 % out of balance compared to the smaller value at any time. The same can be seen in Table 7. The most difference between the test periods is again seen in the losses, this time with the cause seen clearly in the fuel consumption. The average heat from fuel combustion during period 1 is approximately 100 kW lower than during period 2.

Figure 23c presents the heat balance for the overall system level. The heat carried away by the rich gas is the largest heat sink in the system for the whole duration, the next largest is the heat taken away by cooling. At the very start of the experiment the largest heat sink is the heat loss due to the refractory and structure warming up. Combustion is a significant heat

source on the overall system level, which is on a slight decline for the whole duration of the experiment. Table 8 presents the averaged values of the test periods for the whole system.

Table 8. Overall heat balances for averaged periods

Sources/Sinks	Description	Heat [kW]	
		Period 1	Period 2
Sources	comb	1968	1815
	carb	234	236
	FG,in	4.2	6.7
	oxidant	2.5	4.1
	burner,CB	0.35	0.56
	burner,CC	0.1	0.2
	LS,CB	0.0	0.0
	LS,CC	0.0	0.0
	make-up	0.0	0.0
	fuel sensible	0.0	0.0
	Total	2208	2062
Sinks	calc	325	290
	PG	249	252
	FG,out	934	893
	cool	376	409
	loss,CB	109.8	66.5
	loss,CC	164.7	99.7
	FA,CB	8.27	8.53
	FA,CC	42.1	43.1
	Total	2208	2062
Balance	kW	0.0	0.0
	%	0.00	0.00

Here the fluidization air streams of the loop seals and the sensible heat carried by the limestone and fuel appear as zero since they are considered to be at the reference temperature. The reason of the error of zero is that the losses are calculated based on the difference in the total heat balance which in turn balances out the total heat balance. The perfect balance is an unrealistic assumption and might introduce some error. A non-zero heat balance means that there is an on-going change in temperature or mass, which happens frequently in the system. However, since in this case the temperatures are measured and not calculated based on balances the important results remain accurate enough. The largest difference in the fuel feed, which was already seen in Table 7, is even clearer in the overall balance. The lower fuel feed at same the temperatures is, again, the result of the refractory temperature climbing closer to the reactor temperature over time.

The material balances for the same control volumes are shown in Table 9, which includes the molar flows of the main gas species CO₂, O₂, N₂ and H₂O and main solids species CaO

and CaCO_3 in and out of the system as well as the changes due to reactions. The table only presents the data for period 1 due to period 2 being very similar. The mass flow of fuel is ignored in the table as it is considered to be totally consumed and won't effect the balance.

Table 9. Material balances for main gas and solids species for period 1

Source/Sink	Location	Molar flow rate [mol/s]						Total mol/s
		CO ₂	O ₂	N ₂	H ₂ O	CaO	CaCO ₃	
Carbonator								
In	FG,in	1.16	2.13	7.75	0.07			11.11
	burner,CB	0.10	0.18	0.65	0.01			0.93
	toCB		0.77	2.85		16.90	0.21	20.74
	LS,CB		0.65	2.40				3.05
	Total	1.25	3.73	13.65	0.07	16.90	0.21	35.82
Out	cyclone,CB	0.07	2.97	11.37	0.07	0.20	0.02	14.70
	toCC		0.61	2.28		14.59	1.12	18.61
	Total	0.07	3.58	13.65	0.07	14.79	1.14	33.31
Reactions	carb	-1.31				-1.31	1.31	-1.31
	comb,CB	0.13	-0.14					-0.01
	Total	-1.18	-0.14	0.00	0.00	-1.31	1.31	-1.32
Balance	mol/s	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.80	0.38	1.18
	%	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.1	25.1	3.4
Calcliner								
In	oxidant	7.10	4.20	0.00				11.29
	burner,CC	0.27	0.16	0.00				0.43
	toCC		0.61	2.28		14.59	1.12	18.61
	LS,CC		0.81	3.00				3.81
	make-up						0.94	0.94
Total	7.36	5.78	5.29	0.00	14.59	2.06	35.08	
Out	cyclone,CC	13.39	0.84	3.95	3.83	0.68	0.01	22.70
	toCB		0.77	2.85		16.90	0.21	20.74
	Total	13.39	1.60	6.81	3.83	17.58	0.22	43.44
Reactions	calc	1.83				1.83	-1.83	1.83
	comb,CC	4.20	-4.60		3.42			3.02
	Total	6.03	-4.60	0.00	3.42	1.83	-1.83	4.84
Balance	mol/s	0.00	-0.43	-1.52	-0.41	-1.16	0.01	-3.51
	%	0.0	-36.7	-28.7	-12.0	-7.1	5.8	-8.8
Overall system								
In	FG,in	1.16	2.13	7.75	0.07			11.11
	oxidant	7.10	4.20	0.00				11.29
	burner,CB	0.10	0.18	0.65	0.01			0.93
	burner,CC	0.27	0.16					0.43
	LS,CB		0.65	2.40				3.05
	LS,CC		0.81	3.00				3.814
	make-up						0.94	0.939
	Total	8.62	8.12	13.80	0.07	0.00	0.94	31.56
Out	cyclone,CB	0.07	2.97	11.37	0.07	0.20	0.02	14.70
	cyclone,CC	13.39	0.84	3.95	3.83	0.68	0.01	22.70
	Total	13.47	3.81	15.32	3.90	0.88	0.03	37.40
Reactions	combustion	4.34	-4.75		3.42			3.01
	carbonation	-1.31				-1.31	1.31	-1.31
	calcination	1.83				1.83	-1.83	1.83
	Total	4.85	-4.75	0.00	3.42	0.51	-0.51	3.52
Balance	mol/s	0.00	-0.43	-1.52	-0.41	-0.36	0.40	-2.33
	%	0.0	-12.8	-11.0	-11.8	-70.7	93.2	-6.6

The carbonator side material balance shown in Table 9 is well in balance. “carb” in the carbonator balance, at approximately 1.3 mol/s, is considered to be the amount of CO₂

captured, and is almost equal to the amount of CO₂ fed into the carbonator as part of the simulated flue gases and released in char combustion meaning that the carbonator captures CO₂ efficiently.

The calciner section indicates unbalances. The flow of N₂ derived from the composition measurements of the rich gas, shown on the row “cyclone,CC”, gives nearly 1.3 times the amount of nitrogen compared to the amount that is calculated from the N₂ flows introduced into the system, shown on the total row in the “In” section. This indicates that there is a an N₂ stream that is not apparent or that the measurements are somehow diluted by N₂ decreasing the concentrations of other gases.

Figure 24. Product gas concentration comparison

This is also clear when comparing the product gas molar concentrations calculated using the different methods shown in Figure 24, where “method” refers to the results derived directly from the measurement data and “calc” refers to the results derived from the calculated sources and sinks. The full outlet gas compositions are examined closer in the next chapter. The lower N₂ concentration in turn increases the share of other gases in the calculated values, but the difference is only truly visible in the concentration of CO₂ as it has the highest concentration and as O₂ and H₂O are dependent on the combustion of fuel which in turn is based on the fuel feed and consumption of O₂ which is directly based on the measurement data. This missing gas flow could be some leaking gas or a gas flow that is used for instrument cleaning. Adding a multiplier or an additional supply of nitrogen will complete the nitrogen balance, but since there were no facts to base this additional supply on, it was

not considered, and the results are presented with the error in mind. To allow for easy testing and control of results a set of multipliers were installed to the tool.

5.3 Compositions and Transfer

This subchapter presents the compositions of the gases at the outlets of the reactors as well as the compositions and the flow rates of the solids transfer. The solids sample analysis data from the standpipes of both sides was used. The solids transfer rate chosen for the generation of the results shown in the work is the one calculated with the carbonator heat balance.

Figure 25. Gas and solid phase CO₂ comparison

Figure 25 presents one of the most important validation methods, the comparison between the amount of CO₂ captured from the flue gases calculated using the CO₂ balance of the carbonator and that calculated using the determined transfer rate and measured carbonate content. The points at the intersection of approximately 1.2 on both axes are those from the test periods. This indicates that the calculation for this part is accurate.

Figure 26. Flue gas out (a) & product gas (b) molar compositions

Figure 26a shows that by far the largest concentration at the carbonator outlet is N₂ with O₂ following at a quite normal atmospheric concentration. It is evident that there is nearly no CO₂ present in the flue gases after they have passed through the carbonator, which is also seen from the gas balance presented in Figure 26a.

The most abundant gas in the product gases is CO₂ at approximately 60 % on a wet molar basis as seen in Figure 26b. During the testing, a large portion of the CO₂ in the product gas is originating from the simulated recirculation gas fed along with the oxidant. The share of this CO₂ flow is approximately 50 %. The switch from air-firing to oxy-combustion can be observed at the beginning and the end of the chart where CO₂ and N₂ effectively switch concentrations. The origins of the CO₂ in the product gas are looked at with more detail in Figure 29.

Similar trends can be observed in CO₂, NO_x and SO₂ in the product gas. All are largely affected by the combustion of fuel shown previously Figure 21b in which the same trends can also be seen. During long periods of the tests, no measurement of CO was recorded in the product gas, however, at carbonator outlet, a concentration of approximately 100 to 300 ppm of CO was measured while nearly no SO₂ or NO_x were measured. The emissive species measurements are taken from the FTIR data.

Figure 27. Solids transfer rates with different calculation methods

The different methods of calculating the solids transfer rates are relatively close to each other with both of the riser calculations returning very similar values. The highest values are obtained using the loop seal heat balances. The values given by the loop seal heat balances can be lowered by assuming a larger correction value for the loop seal fluidization air or in the case of calciner loop seal, a heat source from combusting of char. The rates shown in the figure assume no correction of loop seal fluidization gas measurements and no combustion or calcination inside the loop seals. The comparison between the solids transfer rate \dot{m}_{toCB} and the once-through method as previously described in chapter 4.5 gives an average difference value of 3% with a standard deviation of 0.8 %. When comparing the solids transfer rates together, one needs to keep in mind that other parameters are calculated using only the selected transfer rate which results in the other transfer rates being affected by the chosen rate.

5.4 Key Performance Indicators

This subchapter presents the relevant and CaL-specific parameters as averages and examines some with more detail as a figure in the same manner as previously seen. Table 10 presents the averaged parameters in a single compiled table. The parameters and their meaning are then discussed in text with the detailed figures for some.

Table 10. KPIs for averaged test periods

KPI	Symbol	Unit	Value	
			Period 1	Period 2
carbonator efficiency	E_{carb}	%	94.7	94.8
calciner efficiency	E_{calc}	%	85.4	81.8
total CO ₂ capture efficiency	E_{tot}	%	96.2	94.6
solids transfer ratio	Φ	mol _{CaO} /mol _{CO₂}	13.5	12.8
make-up ratio	Λ	mol _{CaCO₃} /mol _{CO₂}	0.75	0.74
solids transfer rate	\dot{m}_{toCB}	kg/s	1.04	1.00
	\dot{m}_{toCC}	kg/s	1.08	1.04
specific solids transfer rate	$G_{s,carb}$	kg/(m ² s)	3.43	3.32
	$G_{s,calc}$	kg/(m ² s)	2.38	2.31
molar carbonate content	X_{carb}	x%	6.4	5.7
	X_{calc}	x%	1.1	1.4
avg. max. CO ₂ carrying cap.	X_{ave}	x%	26.9	26.8
specific solids inventory	$W_{s,CB}$	kg/m ²	510	513
	$W_{s,CC}$	kg/m ²	128	144
fuel input	\dot{m}_{fuel}	kg/s	0.103	0.095
	Q_{fuel}	kW	1968	1815
combustion in CB	-	kg/s	0.003	0.003
		kW	59.9	59.9
combustion in CC	-	kg/s	0.100	0.092
		kW	1908	1755
cooling duty	Q_{cool}	kW	376	409
specific heat consumption	-	MJ/kg _{CO₂captured}	7.42	7.51
specific oxygen consumption	-	kg _{O₂} /kg _{CO₂captured}	0.53	0.54
grid gas superficial velocity	$u_{grid,CB}$	m/s	2.56	2.56
	$u_{grid,CC}$	m/s	2.25	2.13
top gas superficial velocity	$u_{top,CB}$	m/s	2.99	2.99
	$u_{top,CC}$	m/s	4.09	3.89
CB emissions				
NOx	$c_{NOx,wet}$	ppm	3.39	2.65
CO	$c_{CO,wet}$	ppm	175	109
SO ₂	$c_{SO2,wet}$	ppm	0.00	7.14
CC emissions				
NOx	$c_{NOx,wet}$	ppm	128	125
	-	mg/MJ	45	44
CO	$c_{CO,wet}$	ppm	1.4	2.5
	-	mg/MJ	0.46	0.82
SO ₂	$c_{SO2,wet}$	ppm	5.51	5.12
	-	mg/MJ	4.08	3.88
excess air factor	λ	-	1.08	1.12

A more detailed look into the efficiencies of the system, presented in Figure 28, indicates that the efficiencies stay at the expected levels for the whole duration of the experiment except for, again, the beginning and the end of the experiment.

Figure 28. CaL efficiencies

When looking at E_{calc} and the temperature graphs of the calciner riser presented in Figure 21a, the same deviations can be seen in both graphs. As mentioned previously E_{tot} remains the highest for the whole duration but only with a slight margin. The carbonate content values shown in the table are close according to the efficiencies indicating sufficient capture rate and calcination. E_{tot} typically achieves values between up to 95 % (Haaf, 2020). According to literature such as (Arias, et al. 2024), carbonator efficiencies as high as 99 % have already been demonstrated.

Typical values of solids transfer ratio Φ in CaL pilots are between 2.6 and 20 mol_{CaO}/mol_{CO₂} (Ströhle, et al. 2020; Diego, et al. 2020). In periods 1 and 2 this value is approximately 14 mol_{CaO}/mol_{CO₂}, indicating that there is plenty of CaO available for carbonation. The sensitivity of the carbonator efficiency to changes in the make-up ratio is inversely proportional to the solids transfer ratio. The transfer ratio is determined by the CO₂ carrying capacity of the sorbent. A high transfer ratio makes it possible to achieve a high carbonator efficiency even with a low make-up ratio and low sorbent activity. A low make-up ratio means that new limestone is not needed as much, which will be financially more sustainable.

The make-up ratios in the test periods examined in Table 10 are very high. Typically, the values of Λ for pilots are in the range of 0.05–0.35 mol_{CaO}/mol_{CO₂}. (Ströhle, et al. 2020; Haaf, et al. 2020) High make-up ratio values may be caused by high sorbent loss rates. High make-up flows will only be acceptable in cement or lime applications where the limestone lost as CaL purge and as FA could be utilized as feedstock.

The typical values for specific solids transfer rates G_s are often in the range of 1.9–13.4 kg/(m²s) for similar sized pilots. (Ströhle, et al. 2020; Diego, et al. 2020). The values obtained from the tool are in the lower end of this range. The cross-sectional area of the carbonator riser is slightly smaller than that of the calciner's, this in addition to the slightly different mass flow rate due to the transfer of mass between the gas and solid phases produces the difference in the reactor specific G_s values.

The dimensional aspect can also be seen in the specific solids inventory W_s . Since the carbonator riser is narrower, the mass per area is larger as it is inversely proportional to the cross-sectional area. Referring to literature, $W_{s,carb}$ and $W_{s,carb}$ are shown to have values between 300 to 700 kg/m² and 150 to 300 kg/m² respectively (Haaf, 2020).

The values of specific heat consumption and specific oxygen consumption are important values as they directly indicate the requirement of fuel and the requirement of the oxy-combustion oxidant per amount of CO₂ captured. Possible further research includes calculating these values for CO₂ avoided.

Typical superficial gas velocities in a similar sized carbonator risers are approximately between 2.0 and 4.5 m/s and for the calciner risers a little higher at 2.6–6.0 m/s (Ströhle, et al. 2020; Diego, et al. 2020; Arias, et al. 2018; Haaf, et al. 2020). The superficial gas velocities during the tests considered in the work are aligned with the values found in literature.

Figure 29. Origin of CO₂ in product gas

Figure 29 presents the origin of CO₂ in the product gas. Fuel indicates the CO₂ released by the combustion of fuel. Transfer indicates the CO₂ that is carried over from the carbonator as part of the carbonate and then released in calcination reaction inside the calciner. Make-up indicates the CO₂ that is released in the calcination of the fresh make-up limestone. Ideally the higher the share of the transfer, the more efficient the process is. In the experiment shown in the figure, numerous pilot scale limitations did apply, which impacted this split significantly.

Figure 30. Calciner NO_x emissions as function of lambda

Figure 30 presents the NO_x emissions in the product gas as a function of lambda. A clear correlation between the two can be observed as the trendlines increase along with the

increase of lambda. The different colour data represent the test periods. This is expected as it is well known that that NO_x emission is proportional to lambda. The results of CO emissions are not presentable as there are near to no recordings for the concentration of CO. As mentioned before, FTIR measurements were used to obtain the emissive species concentrations.

6 Conclusions

The main objective of this thesis was to develop a calculation tool in Excel with VBA macros and apply it to experimental data from the La Pereda CaL pilot plant. The tool was used to obtain process parameters and CaL-specific KPIs by solving the material and heat balances. The tool was created to support the scaling-up of the process. The development and application of the tool was successful as it provided good logical results that are in line with other research.

To give a strong background for the purpose of the tool, a literature review was conducted on the current trends in GHG and CO₂ emissions, on how carbon capture can be utilized in mitigating emissions and limiting the global warming, and on the CaL process. The literature review concludes that the most optimistic scenario limits global warming to 1.9 °C when all UN countries have signed NDCs and that if all currently announced CC projects are completed, the CO₂ capture capacity could reach up to over 6 GtCO₂.

The calculation tool utilizes VBA macros as they allowed the tool to be built to visually represent the CaL system with the calculations happening in their respective places on the worksheet. The tool solves the solids transfer rates by first solving the heat balances of the system by iterating the process parameters using the provided measurement data. The error of the heat balances ranged up to ±3 %, while the material balances were in the range of ±7 %. The largest error in the balances was caused by imbalances in N₂ flows. The calculated solids transfer rate at steady state resulted in a transfer rate of approximately 1.1 kg/s with an average difference between calculation methods of 9 %. The method of the calciner loop seal was left out of the comparison.

The CaL efficiencies during the experiment evaluated in the work reached up to 96 % for the total CO₂ capture efficiency and 95 % and 84 % for the carbonator and calciner efficiencies respectively. The results indicated that the specific heat consumption was approximately 7.5 MJ/kg_{CO₂captured} while the specific oxygen consumption was approximately 0.5 kg_{O₂}/kg_{CO₂captured}, both of which are high, but expected for a pilot scale plant. Similarly, the make-up ratio of approximately 0.65 mol_{CaCO₃}/mol_{CO₂} is too high for full scale operation but an expected pilot scale limitation. The solids transfer ratio obtained

from the tool was approximately $14 \text{ mol}_{\text{CaO}}/\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2}$. The emissions and lambda indicate clear and expected correlations.

The main limitations in the work are related to the measurement accuracy and intervals, for example, in the solids sample analysis. Extended development includes improvements, for example, in the averaging methods. Other extended research in the topic includes, for example, gathering more measurement data at the site with especial focus on the intervals of solids sampling, as well as possible flow rate measurements of the solids and of the gas at the exits of each cyclone. Both would revolutionize the solving process of the material and heat balances as well as improve the accuracy of the results at non-steady states and at extremes. Further development of the tool includes adding calculations for residence time as well as a structured sensitivity analysis.

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